

Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance in CCECC Limited (China Civil Engineering Construction Corporation Nigeria)

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Abstract:

The paper examine the effect of motivation on the performance of employees using the case of CCECC, Nigeria. This study was guided by the following research questions (i) what is the impact of motivational goal-setting on performance of employees? (ii) What is the effect of financial incentives on employee performance? (iii) How do recognition and reward programs affect performance. The target population for this study was all the employees of CCECC Nigeria at the headquarters in Lagos. A descriptive research design was adopted. The census technique was used in the study to select the respondents from the list of employees provided by the human resource department in order to capture the entire population, thus, the sample size of the study was 50. The research was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 24. The study revealed that the management of CCECC partially used motivational goal-setting to motivate their employees. The study also showed that there was a lack of regular training and development for the employees to improve their key skills and knowledge and this is an area that should be addressed. Therefore, the management should re-structure the goals they provide and implement mentorship and training programs. The study concluded that the company partially used recognition and reward programs but they were not effective in motivating employees to perform. It was revealed that pay received and the benefits package was not viewed by the employees as being competitive when compared to other construction organizations. The study concluded that money was a highly motivating factor for the employees and management should look into increasing the monetary and benefits package they give. The current recognition and reward programs were perceived by the employees as being inequitable and unfair. Therefore, the study recommends that management re-evaluates and re-engineers the current recognition and reward program and therefore change the perception of the employees about it.

Keywords: Employee Motivation, Employee performance, Goal-Setting, Financial Incentives, Recognition and Reward, Employee training.

Introduction

Motivation has also been described as the process of sustaining goal-directed behavior (Nelson, 2013). It is commonly agreed that there are two types of motivation, namely extrinsic and intrinsic. Intrinsic motivation is that behavior which an individual produces because of the pleasant experiences associated with the behavior itself (Mosley, Pietri and Mosley Jnr, 2012). They stem from motivation that is characteristic of the job itself. Examples are receiving positive recognition, appreciation, a sense of achievement and meeting the challenge. Mosley, Pietri and Mosley Jnr. (2012) describe extrinsic motivation as the behavior performed, not for its own sake, but for the consequences associated with it. Examples include salary, benefits and working conditions. Employees are motivated by a combination of both factors at any given point in time

Employee turnover is a universal problem that all organizations around the world face (Stanley, 2012). One of the factors that contribute to high employee turnover is demotivation (Mosley, Pietri and Mosley Jnr, 2012. All organizations must ensure that their human resources are well satisfied of their welfare as well as working conditions, so as to enhance their optimal and positive contribution to the mission and goals of their respective organizations. An organization should be in a position to identify human resource needs that satisfy the employees at their places of work as they are the most valuable assets in an organization. Without them, an organization is prone to deterioration leading to lack of success (George and Jones, 2013). Essentially, there is always a gap between an individual's actual state of satisfaction and some desired state. Managers try to reduce this gap through motivation (Aguinis, 2012).

Problem statement

According to Certo (2006), good performance is not as a result of motivation only, but also includes ability i.e. skills, equipment, supplies and time. This study sought to answer the following questions (1) Is there a significant effect between goal setting and performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos? (2) Is there a significant effect between financial incentives/monetary factors and the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos? (3) Does recognition and reward programs have impact on the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos?

Literature review:

Employee motivation

(Mullins, 2006). posit that motivated employees are enthusiastic to exert a certain level of effort (intensity), for a certain amount of time (persistence), toward a distinct goal or direction (Mullins, 2006) Motivation and learning theories suggest that pay should be based on performance (Georges and Jones, 2013) Motivation is central to any discussion of work behavior because it is believed that it has a direct link to good work performance; it is assumed that the motivated worker is the productive worker (Riggio, 2014). Motivation and learning theories suggest that pay should be based on performance (Georges and Jones, 2013). Fredrick Herzberg developed a theory of motivation that highlighted the role of job satisfaction in determining worker motivation (Riggio, 2014). He proposed that the determinants of job satisfaction were different from those of job dissatisfaction. The factors giving rise to satisfaction were called motivators (e.g. recognition, responsibility and achievement), while those giving rise to dissatisfaction were called hygiene factors. Aguinis (2012) posit that motivation is regarded as the factors that influence employees to behave in a certain ways. He further emphasized that desires, wants, wishes, aims, goals, needs, drives, motives and incentives are components of motivation. Oribabor (2000) postulated that for employee to be motivated individual must perceive the marginal amount of money offered for their performance as being significant and also individual must attribute important to money. Hersberg (2009) suggested that employee's motivation towards an action at a given period of time would be determined by his values of the outcome at that given time. Employee motivation is an important aspect of an organization because it is an inducement to change people's behavior (kalleberg, 1977). Physiological needs is the most basic level in the hierarchy of needs compared to safety needs and esteem needs (Ahmad, 2012). Non-financial employees motivation is a process by which employees are motivated by non-financial means which are employees participation in decision making and the job itself, creating an atmosphere of positive relaxation, acknowledging the accomplishment and performance of employees in the organization and developing employees skills in terms of training and development (Skinner, N. 2010). Motivation can be of intrinsic and extrinsic form. intrinsic are responsibility or freedom to act while extrinsic motivation includes rewards, promotion, praise, disciplinary actions, criticism and punishment (Khan, 2012).

Employee performance

Cole and Kelly (2011) describe performance as a continuous process for improving the performance of individuals by aligning actual performance with that desired (and with the strategic goals of the organization) through a variety of means such as standard-setting, appraisal and evaluation both informally, day-to-day, and formally/systematically through appraisal interviews and goal-setting. Job performance is defined as the value of the set of employee behaviors that contribute, either positively or negatively to organizational goal accomplishment while task performance are employee behaviors that are directly involved in the transformation of organizational resources into the goods or services that the organization produces (Colquitt, Lepine and Wesson, 2014)

Financial Incentives

McChilloh (2001) posits that financial incentives mean any inducement involving the payment of money and reduction in price paid for goods or services or any award of credit. Financial incentives enhance the employment relationship because it creates the basis for high levels of commitment and therefore, firms must develop strategies that include financial incentives and rewards for example promotion, bonus, profit sharing or gain sharing and employees stock ownership etc (Ismail, Guatleng, Chhekiong, and Ibrahim, 2009). Money is the principal inducement and no other incentive comes close to it with respect to its influential value (Locke and

Latham, 1990). Money has the dominancy to magnetize, retain and motivate individuals towards higher performance (Stanley, 2012) The fact that employees fear losing their job makes money an extremely effective motivator because it is indispensable for survival in an economy (Cole, 2000). Fredrick Taylor has described money as the most fundamental factor in motivating the industrial workers' to attain greater productivity (Steers and Porter, 2011). It is therefore imperative that organizations think critically about the remuneration packages that they offer to their employees. According to Kinicki and Kreitner (2016), financial incentives are more effective when they are linked to (or contingent upon) good performance. A key principle is for managers to explain clearly to employees how performance is linked to pay, including the fact that unethical behavior will not be tolerated as a way of attaining a performance goal (Steers and Porter, 2011). Whether in the form of wages, piecework, incentive, pay bonuses, stock options, or any other things that may be given to employees for performance. Money is a crucial factor. Money is more than monetary value; it can also mean status or power. Economists and most managers tend to place money high on the side of motivators whereas behavioral scientists tend to place it low. Probably neither view is right (Mullins, 1996). However, if money is to be a motivator, then managers must remember certain things. Money is likely to be more important to people who are raising a family, that to people who have „arrive“ in the sense that their monetary needs are not so urgent. Money is urgent means of achieving a minimum standard of living though this has a way of getting higher as people become more affluent. Compensation is one of the physical needs that influence motivation which in turn will affect the employee performance (Hersberg, 2009). Compensation has a big influence in the recruitment of employees, motivation productivity and employee turnover (Steers and Porter, 2011). Financial incentives are largely regarded as an adequate means to motivate employees and to improve their performance (Smith and Hitt, 2005).

Effectiveness of employee training and development

Employee Development Programs are designed to meet specific objectives, which contribute to both employee and organizational effectiveness. There are several steps in the process of management development (Kulkarni, 2013:139). These includes reviewing organizational objectives, evaluating the organization's current management resources, determining individual needs, designing and implementing development programs and evaluating the effectiveness of these programs and measuring the impact of training on participants quality of work life. In simple way, it can be denoted as per the following formula (Kulkarni, 2013): Employee Development = Employee Education + Employee Skills + Training Effectiveness + Employee Quality of work life. Adeniyi (1995) Staff training and development is a work activity that can make a very significant contribution to the overall effectiveness and profitability of an organization. Training and development aim at developing competencies such as technical, human, conceptual and managerial for the furtherance of individual and organization growth (Oribabor,2000) Stavrou et al., (2004) The main goal of training is to provide, obtain and improve the necessary skills in order to help organizations achieve their goals and create competitive advantage by adding value to their key resources i.e. managers. Training programme is dependent on the following parameters for its success (i) perceived value of leaning programme (ii) attitude to teacher (iii) response to learning conditions (iv) desire to learn: the degree to which trainees really want to learn and do well (Chih , Li and Lee 2008) Bates and Davis (2010) Usefulness of training programme is possible only when the trainee is able to practise the theoretical aspects learned in training programme in actual work environment. They highlighted the use of role playing, cases, simulation, mediated exercises, and computer based learning to provide exposure to a current and relevant body of knowledge and real world situations. Kalaiselvan and Naachimuthu (2011) Training cost and business benefits are drawn on X and Y axis respectively. Four quadrants were identified to highlight (i) strategic (Lower training cost and higher business benefits), (ii) Payback (Higher training cost and higher business benefits) (iii) Think (Lower training cost and lower business benefits) (iv) Drop (Higher training cost and higher business benefits). Karthik R (2012) Training objectives tell the trainee that what is expected out of him at the end of the training program. Training objectives are of great significance from a number of stakeholder perspectives; Trainer, trainee, designer, evaluator.

Development of Hypotheses

In the light of the literature, we argue and propose the hypotheses following:

H1: Motivational goal setting does not significantly affect the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos.

H2: Financial incentives/monetary factors does not significantly affect the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria Lagos.

H3: Recognition and reward programs does not significantly affect the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos.

Methodology

The exploratory research design used in this study was a study of CCECC Nigeria Limited. Descriptive research design was used in this study. The study population was composed of a total of 50 employees of the organization. The study population refers to the total collection of elements which one would like to study or make inferences (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2013). The research design for this study was the survey research design to assess the relationship between the effect of motivation and employee performance. This was therefore qualitative and quantitative in nature. The sampling technique used was convenient sampling. According to Mugo (2010), a convenient sample results when the more convenient units are chosen from a population for observation. The study population will be segmented into four groups: The engineers at field, Finance, Admin and Supervisor/Manager. This will ensure representation across the various departments. Considering that, the nature of the sampling technique selected for the study was a census, the sample size of the study was all the 50 employees that work at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos. The type of data collected was primary data and the collection tool was a self administered questionnaire given to all CCECC Nigeria Lagos employees. The first part of the questionnaire collected demographic data of the respondents such as age group, gender and department. The second part was concerned with the effect of goal setting on motivation. There were five multiple choice options representing five levels of preference, that is; Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neither Agree or Disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree. The third part of the questionnaire looks at rewards and recognition and their effect on employee motivation with five preferences indicated, that is; Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neither Agree or Disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree. The fourth part looks at the effect of financial incentives on employee motivation and performance and offers multiple choice options representing five levels of preference, that is; strongly disagree, Disagree, Neither Agree or Disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree. The data collected was coded and captured into the computer for analysis using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24. The data was then presented in a convenient and informative way including frequency tables, graphs and charts for easier analysis and interpretation. Descriptive analysis was used to determine the proportions and frequency of the variables. Correlation tests were used to draw inferences about the population from the sample and Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) was used to facilitate the data analysis.

Analysis, Finding and Interpretation of Results

Response Rate

50 questionnaires were distributed to the population and 48 were received. After cleaning the data by carefully scrutinizing the data to ensure all questions were filled appropriately, 46 remained, giving this study a response rate of 92%. The response rate is the extent to which the final set of data includes sample members and is calculated from the number of people with whom interviews are completed, divided by the total number of people in the entire sample, including those who refused to participate and those who were unavailable (Koltler, 1997).

Gender

The respondents were asked to indicate their gender and the results which were obtained where 61% of the respondents were male and 39% were female, there by indicating that female and 39% were male were 61, there by indicating that CCECC Nigeria, Lagos has more male employees compare to female employees

Age Group

The respondents were asked to indicate the age group the belonged to and the results shows that 17% of the respondents are below 25 years of age, 26% are between 26-30 years, 28% are between 31-35 years, 20% are between 36-40 years while 9 % are above 41 years of age. This shows that majority of the respondents are aged between 31 and 35 years

Department

The respondents were asked to indicate the department they worked in and the results shows that 37% of the respondents are field engineers, 9% work in the administrative department, 24% are in supervision, 20% are in finance and 11% are in other departments namely legal and architectural departments respectively. The results show that agents constitute the largest department with 37% of the total respondents.

Tenure

The respondents were asked to indicate the number of years they had worked in the organization and the results shows that 17% of the respondents have worked for less than one year, 22% have worked for 1-2 years, 30% have worked for 2-3 years, 22% have worked for 3-4 years and 9% have worked for 5 years and above. This shows that majority of the respondents have worked for 2-3 years

Impact of Motivational Goal-setting on Employee Performance

The respondents were asked to rate various goal-setting factors using the scale 'SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree'. The results of the study were as follows:

Participation in Setting Goals

The respondents were asked whether they are being allowed to them to involve in setting their goals and the results shows that 13% strongly disagreed, 15% disagreed, 22% were neutral, 41% agreed while 9% strongly agreed. This shows that majority of the staffs are being involved in setting their goals.

Importance of Goals

The research shown that 2% strongly disagreed, 9% disagreed, 15% were neutral, 57% agreed while 17% strongly agreed. This indicates that most of the employees understand the importance of their goals in relation to the overall objective of the organization.

Specific Goals

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they have specific goal to aim for within their job and the results shows that 9% strongly disagreed, 9% Disagreed, 24% were neutral, 35% agreed while 24% strongly agreed. This shown that most of the staffs have specific goals to work towards within the context of their jobs.

Realistic and Achievable Goals

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they have realistic and achievable goals to aim for within their job and the results shows that 13% strongly disagreed, 17% disagreed, 22% were neutral, 35% agreed while 11% strongly agreed. This shown that most of the employees agree that they have realistic and achievable goals at work.

Satisfaction with Work Challenges

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they are satisfied with the challenges provided by their jobs and the results shows that 9% strongly disagreed, 24% disagreed, 17% were neutral, 35% agreed while 15% strongly agreed. This shown that majority of the employees agree that they are satisfied with the challenges provided at work.

Difficult Goals at Work

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they have difficult goals at work and the results shows that 17% strongly disagreed, 22% disagreed, 37% were neutral, 15% agreed while 9% strongly agreed. This shown that majority of the employees thought their goals at work were neither difficult nor easy.

Regular Training

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the organization regularly trains them to acquire knowledge and skills and the result shows that 20% strongly disagreed, 26% disagreed, 13% were neutral, 26% agreed while 15% strongly agreed. This results shown that an equal number of the employees both agree and disagree that they undergo regular training to acquire knowledge, skill and attitudes towards their work.

Mentorship

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the organization has assigned them mentors to guide them in achieving their goals and the results shows that 35% strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, 24% were neutral, 17%

agreed while 4% strongly agreed. This results show that majority of the employees do not have a mentor to guide them in achieving their goals

Constructive Feedback

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they received constructive feedback regularly related to their goals and the results shows that 11% strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, 35% were neutral, 28% agreed while 7% strongly agreed. This results show that majority of the employees are neutral regarding constructive feedback that they receive in relation to their goals

Goal-setting

The respondents were asked to indicate whether setting goals had improved their overall performance goals and the results shows that 17% strongly disagreed, 15% disagreed, 30% were neutral, 28% agreed while 9% strongly agreed. This results show that majority of the employees have not seen an improvement of their performance as a result of setting goals.

Relationship between Goal-setting and Employee Performance

H1: motivational goal setting does not significantly affect the performance of employees at CCECC

Nigeria, Lagos

The Pearson correlation test was conducted on goal-setting factors to determine the significance of the factors (the independent variables) and their impact on employee performance (the dependent variable). The study required P value ranged between 0.00 and 0.05 for significant factors.

It shows that participation in setting of goals was significant (P=0.001). Importance of goals in relation to the overall objective of the organization was significant (P=0.007). Use of specific, clear goals to aim for was significant (P=0.002). Use of goals that are realistic and achievable was significant (P=0.000). Satisfaction with challenges provided by work was significant (P=0.000). Difficult and challenging goals to be met at work was significant (P=0.000). Use of training to acquire and improve knowledge, skills and attitudes towards work was significant (P=0.001). Use of mentors at work for guidance in achieving goals was significant (P=0.001). Receiving fair and constructive feedback related to goals was insignificant (P=0.187). Setting of goals has improved overall performance was significant (P=0.000).

Effect of Financial/ Monetary Factors on Employee Performance

The respondents were asked to rate various monetary factors using the scale 'SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree'. The results of the study were as follows:

Satisfaction with Pay

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they were satisfied with the pay/salary they receive and the results shows that 54% strongly disagreed, 11% disagreed, 15% were neutral, 15% agreed while 4% strongly agreed. This results show that majority of the employees are dissatisfied with the level of pay they receive

Competitive Pay

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the pay they receive is competitive when compared to other companies in the industry and the results shows that 44% strongly disagreed, 29% disagreed, 20% were neutral, 7% agreed while 2% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees do not think that the pay offered by the organization is competitive when compared to other companies in the industry

Monthly Expense Allowance

The results show that majority of the employees do not think that the pay offered by the organization is competitive when compared to other companies in the industry. be satisfied if they received a monthly expense allowance and the results shows that 11% strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, 15% were neutral, 33% agreed while 22% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees would be satisfied with a monthly expense allowance package offered by the organization is not competitive.

Competitive Benefits Package

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the benefits package they receive is competitive and the result shows that 28% strongly disagreed, 26% disagreed, 20% were neutral, 24% agreed while 2% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees do not think that the benefits package offered by the organization is not competitive

Money as an Incentive

The respondents were asked to indicate whether money is a crucial incentive to work motivation and the results shows that 7% strongly disagreed, 15% disagreed, 17% were neutral, 20% agreed while 41% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees agree that money is a crucial incentive to work motivation

Salary Dissatisfaction

The respondents were asked to indicate whether their salary and other hygiene factors have led to a dissatisfaction of their employment and the result shows that 11% strongly disagreed, 24% disagreed, 20% were neutral, 28% agreed while 17% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees are dissatisfied with their employment as a result of their salaries, company policies, working conditions and supervision

Profit Sharing

The respondents were asked to indicate whether a profit sharing scheme would motivate them to perform and the results shows that 13% strongly disagreed, 11% disagreed, 24% were neutral, 26% agreed while 26% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees would be motivated to perform better if the company implements a profit sharing scheme

Relationship between Financial/Monetary Incentives and Employee Performance

H2: financial incentives/monetary factors does not significantly affect the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria Lagos.

The Pearson correlation test was conducted on financial/monetary factors to determine the significance of the factors (the independent variables) and their impact on employee performance (the dependent variable). The study required P value ranged between 0.00 and 0.05 for significant factors. it shows that the satisfaction with pay received was significant (P=0.000). Pay being competitive compared to other companies in the industry was significant (P=0.001). Company maintains competitive pay and benefits package was significant (P=0.005). Satisfaction if monthly expense allowance is given was significant (P=0.000). Use of monetary rewards like base pay, commission and bonus was significant (P=0.000). Money being a crucial incentive to work motivation was significant (P=0.000). Salary and other hygiene factors leading to dissatisfaction of employment was significant (P=0.000). Money as a strong indication of the value the organization has placed on services offered was significant (P=0.060). Company pay policy attracts and retain high performing employees was significant (P=0.000). Profit-sharing scheme would motivate employees to perform was significant (P=0.000).

Effect of Recognition and Reward Factors on Employee Performance

The respondents were asked to rate various recognition and reward factors using the scale ‘SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree’. The results of the study were as follows:

Non-monetary Rewards

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the organization uses non-monetary rewards and the results are shown. Table 4.15 shows that 8% strongly disagreed, 13% disagreed, 7% were neutral, 13% agreed while 5% strongly agreed. The results show that an equal number of employees both agree and disagree that the company uses non-monetary rewards to motivate them.

Recognition by Management

The respondents were asked to indicate whether it is important to them to be formally recognized by management and the results are shown. Figure 4.13 shows that 9% strongly disagreed, 9% disagreed, 20% were neutral, 33% agreed while 30% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees would like to be formally recognized by management for a job well done.

Recognition by Co-workers

The respondents were asked to indicate whether it is important to them to be recognized by their co-workers and the results are shown. Figure 4.14 shows that 9% strongly disagreed, 13% disagreed, 24% were neutral, 28% agreed while 26% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees would like to be formally recognized by their co-workers for a job well done

Vouchers

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the company uses gift vouchers, movie tickets or meal vouchers to motivate them and the results are shown. Table 4.16 shows that 39% strongly disagreed, 26%

disagreed, 24% were neutral, 7% agreed while 4% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees would be motivated if the organization used gift and meal vouchers.

Wellness Programs

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the implementation of a wellness program like gym membership would motivate them and the results are shown. Figure 4.15 shows that 17% strongly disagreed, 9% disagreed, 17% were neutral, 24% agreed while 33% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees would be motivated if the organization implemented a wellness program.

Rewards as Goals

The respondents were asked to indicate whether rewards are used as goals that are strived for and the results are shown. Table 4.17 shows that 9% strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, 42% were neutral, 22% agreed while 9% strongly agreed. The results show that majority of the employees were neutral in how they viewed the rewards given by the company.

Training and Development as Rewards

The respondents were asked to indicate whether training and development is used as a reward and the results are shown. Table 4.18 shows that 11% strongly disagreed, 35% disagreed, 22% were neutral, 26% agreed while 7% strongly agreed. The results show that the company does not use training and development as a reward that can motivate employees.

Equitable Reward Scheme

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the current reward scheme was equitable and the results are shown. Figure 4.16 shows that 28% strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, 44% were neutral, 7% agreed while 2% strongly agreed. The results show that the employees do not consider the current reward scheme as equitable or inequitable and may have a sense of apathy towards it.

Increased Performance

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the current recognition and reward program had increased their performance and the results are shown. Figure 4.17 shows that 35% strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, 30% were neutral, 11% agreed while 4% strongly agreed. The results show that the current recognition and reward program does not motivate the employees to increase their motivation.

Relationship between Financial/Monetary Incentives and Employee Performance

H3: recognition and reward programs do not significantly affect the performance of employees at CCECC Nigeria, Lagos

The Pearson correlation test was conducted on financial/monetary factors to determine the significance of the factors (the independent variables) and their impact on employee performance (the dependent variable). The study required P value ranged between 0.00 and 0.05 for significant factors.

Table 4.20 shows that the use of non-monetary factors like inclusive decision-making and flexible working hours was significant (P=0.057). Formal recognition by management for a job well done was significant (P=0.000). Recognition by co-workers for a job well done was significant (P=0.001). Use of non-monetary rewards like gift and meal vouchers was significant (P=0.000). Wellness benefit program for motivation was insignificant (P= 0.079). Use of rewards as goals that employees strive for was insignificant (P= 0.413). Use of training and development for motivation was significant (P=0.003). Company has a fair and equitable reward scheme was significant (P=0.000). Current recognition and reward program boosts motivation was significant (P=0.000)

Conclusions

From the study, it can be concluded that management at CCECC allowed its employees to participate in setting their goals and the employees understood the importance that goals have on the overall performance of the organization. The study also concluded that the goals set were specific and clear but not challenging. Also, there is no constructive feedback, mentorship and training which had an effect on the overall motivation of the employees.

Moreover, the employees viewed the current recognition and reward program as being inequitable. The study found out that the employees of the organization found it important to be recognized by both management and

co-workers for a job well done. From the study, it can be concluded that the organization had not increased performance or observed long term improvement as a result of the reward system in place. The study concluded that employees were not happy with the monetary incentives given by CCECC Nigeria Lagos. It can be observed that the organization did not use monetary rewards to motivate employees and that the employees perceive money as a crucial incentive to work motivation. It can also be concluded that the organization did not have a competitive payment and benefits package when compared to other companies in the industry and additionally, the current pay policy did not attract and retain high performing employees

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